

SYNTHESIS OF TIGHTLY BOUNDED CNT FORESTS ON CARBON FIBERS FOR COMPOSITES

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1. Introduction

Recently, carbon fiber (CF) reinforced polymer composite gets great attraction in the aerospace field due to its excellent properties such as ultra-lightness, high strength and durability.[1-3] Although CF reinforced composites exhibit excellent in-plane properties, they typically show poor out-of-plane performance. Recently, many efforts to solve this problem using a 3 dimensional (3D) structure such as vertically aligned nanomaterials on 2D fiber fabrics and hierarchical structures have been done.[4,5] These attempts, however, could not improve the out-of-plane performance because of the weak adhesion between the nanomaterials and the fiber fabrics. Thus, enhancement of the adhesion between nanomaterials and CF fabrics is a key factor for high out-of-plane performance.

Carbon nanotube (CNT) has extremely high electrical and thermal conductivity. In addition, its mechanical strength surpasses that of CF, and it possesses much larger specific surface area than CF.[6-8] When tightly bound CNT forests are synthesized on the surface of CF to form a hierarchical structure, the contact surface area between CF and polymer will be greatly increased, and the out-of-plane strength may also be improved.

Here, we report the synthesis of tightly bound CNT forests on the surface of CF fabrics for composites.

2. Experiment

2.1 Synthesis of tightly bound CNT forests on CFs

We used commercially available CF (AS4, HexTow) as a starting material. Before the CNT growth, SiO₂ and Al₂O₃ thin-films were deposited on

the surface of CF fabrics by low pressure chemical vapor deposition (CVD) and atomic layer deposition, respectively. A thin layer of Fe (1 nm) was subsequently deposited as a catalyst on the thin-film coated CFs by e-beam evaporation. CNTs growth was carried out in a tube furnace by the thermal CVD technique. The CF fabric was located in a quartz tube furnace and heat-treated at 750 °C under Ar flow. Then the catalyst layer was reduced under the flow of Ar and H₂ at 750 °C. Acetylene gas was introduced for CNT growth for 30 min. After the growth, the sample was cooled to room temperature under Ar.

2.2 Control experiment

Control experiment was designed to investigate the effects of the SiO₂ layer, hence the conditions used were identical, except for the replacement of the SiO₂ layer with Ti thin film. The Ti layer was deposited on the CF by RF-sputter.

2.3 Characterization

The morphology of the synthesized CNT forests on the CFs was observed using a field-emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM, JEOL JMS-7400F, operating at 10 keV). The crystal structures and chemical composition of the formed thin-films on the CFs were observed using a high-resolution scanning transmission electron microscope (Cs corrected HR-STEM, JEOL JEM-2200FS with energy-dispersive X-ray spectrometer (EDX), operating at 200 kV). TEM samples were prepared using a focused ion beam etching machine (FIB, FEI Helios-pegasus).

3 Results and discussion

3.1 CNT forests on the CF

The CNT forests were synthesized by thermal CVD method which is amenable for large-scale synthesis. Figure 1 (a)-(d) show typical FE-SEM images of the adhesion-improved CNT forest grown on the surface of CFs. The length of the CNT forest is 350 μm and the growth rate of the CNT forest was about 10 μm per minute. Figure 1 (c) and (d) show enlarged images taken from the region marked by the squares in Figure 1 (a) and (c), respectively. As shown in Figure 1 (d), the CNTs grew to curl. In a fabrication of composites, the curly structure provides a large contact area between the CNTs and polymers, thus improving the strength of composites.

Figure 1. Adhesion-improved CNT forests on the CFs. (a) side and (b) top view of high-density CNT forests. (c) and (d) show an enlarged SEM images taken from the area marked by the squares in (a) and (c), respectively.

We used EELS technique to confirm the buffer layers and the CNTs. Figure 2 (b)-(g) show EELS mapping images for Fe, Pt, C, O, Si, and Al, respectively. Figure 2(a) shows the TEM image corresponding to the EELS mapping images in Figure 2 (b)-(g). It can be concluded that the SiO_2 and the Al_2O_3 layer were successfully deposited between the CNTs and the CFs.

To improve the adhesion between CNT forests and CFs, SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 thin films were sequentially deposited on the CFs. In the SiO_2 film deposition step, sizing materials on the CFs were removed at high temperature and low pressure.[9] SiC film as a diffusion barrier was formed between SiO_2 layer and CF at high temperature and under a

Si contained gas.[10] The adhesion between the SiO_2 layer and the CF can be enhanced due to the SiC diffusion barrier layer. Since the SiO_2 and the Al_2O_3 layers are similar oxide layers, the adhesion between them is guaranteed. According to a recent report, the Fe nanoparticles as a catalyst for growing CNTs diffused into the buffer layer such as Al_2O_3 during the CNT growth.[11] Due to this reason, Fe nanoparticles may be embedded in the Al_2O_3 layer.

Figure 2. (a) TEM image of the Pt coated CNTs on the CF corresponding to EELS mapping images of (b) Fe, (c) Pt, (d) C, (e) O, (f) Si, and (g) Al elements.

The strength of adhesion between the CNT forests and the CFs was qualitatively assessed using the Scotch-tape test (ASTM D3359) as shown in Figure 3(a). A photograph of the tape used to Scotch tape test is shown in Figure 3(b). Some CNTs were detached from the CFs and attached to the tape in

Figure 3(d) and (e). Most CNT forests, however, still remained on the CFs as shown in Figure 3(c). Among the scale of grade 0~5 (ASTM D3359), the adhesion-improved CNT forests has an excellent adhesion with a grade 5. As a result of tape test, we confirmed that the adhesion between CNT forests and CFs was dramatically improved.

Figure 3. (a) Schematic diagram of the Scotch tape test. (b) The tape after the test. The SEM images of (c) CF and (d) tape side after Scotch tape test. (e) An enlarged SEM image taken from the area marked by dotted circle in (d).

Figure 4. CNT forests on the CFs with a Ti adhesion layer between the Al_2O_3 layer and the CF. (a) side and (b) tilt view of high-density CNT forests.

3.2 Control experiment

Figure 4 (a) and (b) show SEM images of the CNT forest on the CF with a Ti thin film as an adhesion layer between the buffer layer and the CF.

Figure 5(a) shows a photograph of the tape used to Scotch tape test using the specimen with Ti layer instead of SiO_2 layer. After the Scotch tape test, most CNTs were detached from the CFs in Figure 5(b). Figure 5 (c) shows most CNT forests moved to tape side. Among the scale of grade 0~5 (ASTM

D3359), the CNT forests on CF with Ti film has a poor adhesion with a grade 0-1.

Although the CNT forests were uniformly grown on the surface the CF, the adhesion between Ti and CF is not good because the diffusion barrier layer was not formed between the Ti film and CF. Hence the CNT forests were detached easily from the CFs

Figure 5. (a) The tape after the test. The SEM images of (b) CF and (d) tape side after Scotch tape test. (c) and (e) Enlarged SEM images taken from the area marked by dotted circle in (b) and (d), respectively.

4. Conclusions

We successfully synthesized the adhesion-improved CNT forests on CFs. We assessed the adhesion between CNT forests and CFs using the Scotch-tape test (ASTM D3359). The specimens, tightly bound CNT forests grown on CF fabrics, were supplied to T. H. Hahn's group for the fabrication of composites, and further evaluation.

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